

Evolving Cryptography: Classical Frameworks, Quantum Challenges, and Post-Quantum Approaches

1 Introduction

Cryptography is the method used for securing sensitive information using mathematical techniques and coding algorithms in a way that only authenticated users can decipher the information for the use of data. It ensures the information transmitted is secure, private, confidential, and accessible solely by intended recipients. The features of cryptography include confidentiality, integrity, authentication, non-repudiation, and key management. Cryptography should be efficient, flexible, resistant to attacks, and secure. Even though not mandatory, most modern cryptography frameworks are based on a way to function with a trapdoor. Thus, facilitating easy encryption and decryption for the user with knowledge of the trapdoor function and challenges in the absence of it.

2 Types of Cryptography

The three types of classification of cryptography are symmetric, asymmetric, and hash functions. Symmetric encryption is when both sender and receiver share the same secret key, there are mainly two types of symmetric encryption such as block ciphers and stream ciphers. The most used of these is AES, it is considered secure even against quantum attacks as of current knowledge if the key size is large enough. However, the disadvantage here is the need to transmit the secret key causing concerns of attacks. It is widely used for Bulk messages. Asymmetric encryption is one of the most used and reliable cryptography. The most used of these are RSA and ECC. They are efficient but currently under quantum threat. Hash functions are typically non-invertible conversions of data where the hashed functions are employed for data integrity verification and authentication.

3 Requirements of cryptography

The most used math in cryptography is modular arithmetic, number theory, and abstract algebra due to ease of solving, and extensive research availability. The current focus is also being shifted toward algebraic geometry. The security frameworks also encompass pre-image resistance, and collision resistance, maintain pseudo randomness, should be computationally complex to withstand attacks, and mathematically hard to crack. The conditions for the framework to be potentially sound for asymmetric encryption are it needs to be quantum attack resistant, mathematically hard, one-way function which is easier in one direction but computationally complex the other way without trapdoor function, bijective mapping, resistance against backdoor attacks, cryptanalysis resistant, efficient, secure and scalable.

4 Classical Cryptography

[1] Advanced Encryption Standard

Advanced Encryption Standard [1] was published by NIST in 2001. It is a symmetric key algorithm that uses a block cipher. AES currently has 3 key lengths being used: 128 bits with 10 rounds, 192 bits with 12 rounds, and 256 bits with 14 rounds. The message is divided into 128-bit blocks and the key is further used

to create 10 subkeys each of 128 bits. The four main steps involved are byte substitution where data is replaced by the data from the s-box, shift rows are left shifting the rows of the matrix, mix columns are multiplied by a standard AES specified matrix, add round key is done by XORing the array with 128-bit round key. All the operations are done in a finite field. As of current advancement increasing the key length of AES would make it withstand the quantum threat.

[2] RSA Encryption

RSA[2] is classical cryptographic framework which was published in 1977. It is based on the difficulty of factoring large numbers. The mathematical formulation can be concisely given as:

$$n = p \times q \quad (1)$$

$$\phi(n) = (p - 1) \times (q - 1) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Choose } e \text{ such that } 1 < e < \phi(n) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{gcd}(e, \phi(n)) = 1 \quad (4)$$

$$e \times d \equiv 1 \pmod{\phi(n)} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Cipher} = \text{Message}^e \pmod{n} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Message} = \text{Cipher}^d \pmod{n} \quad (7)$$

RSA is the most widely used algorithm currently due to its performance efficiency and simplicity. The key size is generally 1024 or 2048 bits. The process of period-finding using the Quantum Fourier Transform is used in Shor's algorithm. The Quantum Fourier transform takes some function $f(x)$ and finds out the period of the function. This method is believed to be able to factor large numbers efficiently compared to classical algorithms but currently is not capable of scaling to potential due to qubit limitation.

[3] Elliptic curve cryptography

ECC [5] is considered more secure along with the very short key size, the 256-bit ECC is said to be equivalent to the strength of a 3072-bit RSA key size but not over AES key size. This is very similar to the Diffie-Hellman discrete logarithm. ECC uses point addition of elliptic curve over finite field abelian group for encryption. It requires one-sixth of the computational effort of RSA to provide the same security and is 15 times faster than the same. ECDH and ECDSA are widely used in blockchain cryptography and others. The practical applicability of quantum algorithms is currently limited to quantum system scaling difficulties but concern about the future advancement exists.

5 Quantum Cryptography

Quantum computers [3] are believed to offer certain advantages over classical such as being able to compute certain specific classes of NP and NP-Hard problems in polynomial time due to their superposition, quantum parallelism, quantum entanglement, and other physical properties. Assuming fundamental principles of physics like superposition and entanglement are valid, it could be used efficiently in quantum cryptography for secure communication. QKD

resists eavesdropping to an extent as it causes disturbance in the medium which could be detected, though it is not completely immune to eavesdropping the risks could be mitigated. Its no-cloning

theorem which does not allow duplicate the unknown state to be copied perfectly is an added advantage. QKD [4] is considered very secure and implemented, extensive deployment is under research and is considered currently a very promising avenue.

6 Post-Quantum Cryptography

Post-quantum cryptography is the term coined to represent the crypto schemes that are capable of being secure under quantum and classical threats [6]. Numerous research is being done on exploring different possibilities to tackle the problem of quantum threats. The most prominent asymmetric encryptions are as follows

[1] Lattice-based cryptography

The lattice is based on the shortest or closest vector problem which is considered np hard [7]. The problem on the lattice is considered np-hard but due to its periodic structure and Fourier transformation being the advantage of quantum computers, various methods are being researched to break it. An extension of Shor's algorithm is said to be capable of breaking the hardness of a few lattice problems. Due to its richness lattice is the most widely researched PQC method.

[2] Code-based cryptography

It is also known as error-correcting code cryptography, is based on the error-correcting principle and difficulty of decoding random linear codes. For example, a 64-bit key is stored in 72-bit physical memory, it is designed in such a way that it would be system would be able to detect single-bit or double-bit errors and rectify them.

[3] Hash-based cryptography

hash-based signature relies on the fact that the pre-image detection from the given hashed function is difficult. The conditions for using signatures are that it should not be repeated, the signer must know the function and thus the hashed function could be verified by the receiver. It should be a time function. Grover's algorithm does affect the hash-based function due to its search time reduction.

[4] Multivariate quadratic polynomial cryptography

In the given finite field, finding a set of polynomials of n variables even for smaller degrees is difficult [9]. But checking if the function belongs to the set is easier but finding the solution of the function from the set is infeasible without the private key.

[5] Super-singular ECC isogeny cryptography

Elliptic curves are a very rich field with a vast amount of research done. Elliptic curves are defined over a finite field with the ideal fractional class group that can act freely on them [10]. Using the relation between prime isogenies and ideal the protocol is built which is considered safe against quantum threats. The security relies on the isogeny path problem. Research in these areas to develop robust cryptographic schemes capable of withstanding quantum threats are being explored.

7 Conclusion

Post-quantum cryptography is widely studied and researched both through classical means and quantum computing. It is continuously evolving, and a wide variety of ways are discussed here and many other possibilities are explored. The breakthrough of quantum technology is expected to be near future, and the threats posed are related to the security of the data in the data-driven world. Quantum cryptography offers strong theoretical advantages and is being brought to the real world through many research organisations and startups, but are in preliminary stages of large-scale deployment. Post-quantum cryptography is therefore being explored as a major research direction, with lattice-based, code-based, hash-based, multivariate, and isogeny-based schemes each offering distinct advantages and limitations as discussed in notes. Hybrid approaches are also explored, which could balance the trade-off between future potential and realistic implementation. To conclude, secure communication will depend on developing potential cryptographic frameworks that are robust, efficient, and secure against both classical and quantum threats and increased algorithmic advancements.

8 References

- [1] Dworkin, M. J. (2023). Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.FIPS.197-upd1>
- [2] Rivest, R. L., Shamir, A., & Adleman, L. (n.d.). A Method for Obtaining Digital Signatures and Public-Key Cryptosystems.
- [3] Gokhale, P. (2015, November 16). How does Shor's algorithm work in layman's terms? Retrieved from <https://example.com>
- [4] An overview of Quantum Cryptography and Shor's Algorithm. (2020). *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 9(5), 7487–7495. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijatcse/2020/82952020>
- [5] Hankerson, D., Menezes, A. (2021). Elliptic Curve Cryptography. In: Jajodia, S., Samarati, P., Yung, M. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Cryptography, Security and Privacy*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-27739-9_245-2
- [6] Lanzagorta, M., & Uhlmann, J. (2008). Quantum Computer Science. *Synthesis Lectures on Quantum Computing*, 1(1), 1–124. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2200/s00159ed1v01y200810qmc002>
- [7] Micciancio, D., & Regev, O. (n.d.). Lattice-based Cryptography.
- [8] Bernstein, D. J., & Lange, T. (2017). Post-quantum cryptography. In *Nature* (Vol. 549, Issue 7671, pp. 188–194). Nature Publishing Group. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature23461>
- [9] Goubin, L., & Yang, B.-Y. (n.d.). Multivariate Cryptography.
- [10] de Feo, L. (2017). Mathematics of Isogeny Based Cryptography. Retrieved from <http://arxiv.org/abs/1711.04062>
- [11] JIN, X.-Q., LIU, W.-H., LIU, X., & ZHAO, Z. (2022). *An Introduction to Linear Algebra*. Science Press, EDP Sciences. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1051/978-2-7598-3044-2>
- [12] Cohen, A. M., Cohen, H., Eisenbud, D., Singer, M. F., & Sturmfels, B. (n.d.). *Algorithms and Computation in Mathematics* (Vol. 20).